

Reflecting on educational design practice

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DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845108>

We are a group of ten educational designers at Monash University, drawn from a much larger group of approximately 70 educational designers across all ten faculties and the central learning and teaching office at Monash. We all work in different ways, either on our own or in a team, with different priorities and access to resources, and at different stages of our careers.

We gathered some brief reflections on our practice and experience, with a focus on our professional development, as we believe this might be useful advice for others working in the field. This self-reflective work helps us to gather evidence of our impact, making our third space work more visible, and disentangling the work and ourselves from organisational structures.

After the Slowposium presentation, participants joined the discussion and shared with others their thoughts on the concepts and ideas presented under the sections detailed below, following the instructions to explore the reflections from participants in each section of this site “and use them as a prompt to think about PD opportunities which might resonate with you.”

About our reflections

The reflections are organised into the following sections:

- What do you do, and how did you get here?
- What are the goals of your work, and how do you measure ‘success’?
- What are some of the blockers to success?
- What PD have you found most valuable?
- What further advice do you have for educational designers seeking to progress their careers?

Each of these sections is divided according to the three different levels of educational designer, termed *education developers* in the Canadian literature, classified by Dawson et al. (2010). The North Island College Centre for Teaching and Learning Innovation (Canada) (North Island College, n. d.) built on this work to create ‘competency charts’ which outline the skills, qualities, knowledge and abilities of educational designers at various stages of growth and professional learning.

The three levels are:

1. novice/entry-level (1-5 years)
2. intermediate/associate director (5-7 years)
3. senior/director (7+ years)

The Educational Developers Caucus (Canada) has published a series of Education Developers guides (see Society for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education [Canada], n.d.). These guides prompt us with a range of suggestions to develop our own portfolios of practice, build rapport and trust in our practice, and reflect on our practice.

What do you do, and how did you get here?

Novice 1-5 years

I currently work in two roles, as a casual educational designer, and as a part-time digital learning support officer (providing learning design and LMS administration). I previously worked in teaching, research, and academic support and found that the tasks I was doing were slowly evolving into ed design, as that was what was needed by the teams I worked in, and I had a higher digital literacy than others which made me the best choice at the time.

I am an Educational Designer in a Faculty at Monash University. I worked in learning design and instructional design in various corporate roles for approximately five years before moving in to HE. When I was ready to return to the workforce after my second child, I decided to look for part-time work, so I got a casual role with FAST here at Monash. I was initially placed with the DVCE but came over to the Faculty to assist in their move to 'Flex' unit offerings, and I have never left! I was lucky enough to secure a fixed-term contract position at first and then an ongoing contract. I have now been in the faculty as an ed designer for 4.5 years.

I work as a faculty educational designer, with a focus on assessment design and innovation. I transitioned into educational design after working as a learning skills adviser and teaching associate, with previous experience as a researcher and educator in history. These previous roles involved a lot of teaching and student-facing support, so I developed practical knowledge of student learning across a range of contexts, assessment approaches, etc. Over time I became increasingly interested in the curriculum design and development aspect of my work, in which I collaborated with academics or co-developed curriculum resources to improve student learning experiences and outcomes. This interest led me to educational design.

Intermediate 5-7 years

I work across three domains – educational design, education governance and management, and strategic initiatives. Started off as a STEM Educator while pursuing PhD. After 10 years of teaching experience, I furthered my passion for Higher Education by proactively getting involved in education projects and initiatives across the university including accelerated projects during the COVID era. After a couple of years of intensive experience in Ed Design in one faculty, I transitioned to a different faculty as an Ed Designer driving education transformation (course redesign and accreditation, curriculum revamp, T&R staff development). I now lead a team of four learning and education designers, along with project-based collaboration with T&R staff and teaching fellows.

Working directly with teachers to advise them around student engagement, meaningful assessment, etc. anything in the pedagogy but also EduTech space together with broad strategic educational initiatives at faculty level. I originally started as a teacher (tutor, then lecturer) in my faculty and did that for many years, eventually leading a number of big units myself and engaging in some initial scholarship in the education space. The teaching work dried up however (or rather was not offered on a contract type that was sustainable for me) and I transitioned into an educational designer role in the same faculty.

I support academics in creating high quality educational experiences and outcomes for students. I view it as a jack-of-all-trades type role. I arrived by happy accident really. I had a STEM research background, but followed the education pathway, primarily because I was passionate about education. I enjoyed teaching and I was quite good at it, but I could not keep up with having young children and the out of hours demands. One day I applied for an Educational Designer role in an area where I had both teaching and some discipline expertise and essentially learned on the job and haven't looked back!

Senior 7+ years

I'm a senior educational designer in a faculty, where I manage a small team of educational designers to advise and support our educators in their education practice. I started as a high school teacher, then as a research student I was given an UG teaching load. I worked as a head tutor and lecturer teaching into a variety of units in my department. From there I went into a student-facing academic support role where I saw the myriad challenges students face in their studies. When my current role as an educational designer was advertised, I jumped at the chance to effect curriculum transformation at a more strategic level.

Lead and support educational initiatives and projects across the faculty and university, including the design, delivery, and administration of all units, including the learning management system. Most of my education was completed through distance learning, and later, online education. As a trained teacher, I became deeply interested in designing learning experiences for people. With the rise of online learning, I saw it as an opportunity to future-proof my career in an area I was passionate about. This led me to pursue a Masters of Education (Online Learning and Design) and transition my career into higher education, where I have had the opportunity to grow my skills and expertise.

I inspire positive changes in academic teaching practices through consultation, facilitation of professional development, and supporting teaching excellence. I was an English teacher, student trainer and lecturer overseas before applying for and becoming an Ed Designer.

I am an educational designer who supports educators in all aspects of T+L from course conception and governance, through to development, delivery and evaluation, classroom instruction, EDI/UDL, staff wellbeing, curriculum development, accreditation, assessment innovation, staff training, research (scholarship of T+L) and online lessons and LMS design. I

studied and practised science for many years (since 2010), working as a researcher in laboratory and field contexts. I regularly supplemented my income with tertiary science teaching, in class, computer, laboratory and field settings, coursework and research settings. I really loved teaching, ed design and research, but as ed design was the more attainable and stable of the teaching and research work I had been trained to do (and was doing), I accepted an ed design offer when it was made to me (rather out of the blue, four years ago; my current manager, who at the time I had never met, emailed me one night saying I had come highly recommended for my ed design skills). While I desperately miss science teaching and research, I really enjoy the science education research and educator training I do as part of my ed design role, and much of the foundational scientific content is the same in the science discipline I am now proud to be in. At the end of the day, I have kids and a mortgage so, while I adore the role and am committed to the sector, I would be only telling a half-truth if I suggested that the job security within a Go8 university setting wasn't the lead factor in my being here!

What are your goals and how do you measure success?

Novice 1-5 years

The goals of my work have changed frequently over different roles, but it is always with the greater aim to support quality teaching and learning. I personally measure success in my role by enabling measurable success in others (i.e. seeing what they are able to do with the skills or systems I assist them to develop), and by how the output I produce is utilised by others.

My two specific work goals for this year are –

1. Play a key role in the strategic planning and implementation of innovative and evidenced-based educational practices, specifically the exploration of relevant education technologies where it makes sense to do so, within the faculty, university and wider higher education community. This will be measured through completion and delivery of a number of specific projects.
2. Advising and leading educators in the development of engaging and holistic learning experiences that consider the asynchronous and synchronous spaces as inherently linked, providing research-backed guidance on how to develop engaging and effective learning activities that tell a clear narrative for students. This will be measured through completion of some specific projects – supporting the University LMS upgrade, delivery of ed tech workshops, and general unit design.

More broadly, my own goals for my work revolve around being a trusted T&L advisor, increasing my knowledge & contribution to SoTL, continuing to improve my presentation skills, and working on new & exciting education interventions across the university.

I aim to foster effective and engaging curriculum design and teaching practices among the academics I work with, to enable improved student learning experiences and outcomes. I partially measure success in relation to practical pedagogical/curriculum improvements at the unit and level, e.g. better student engagement, academic performance, progression of skills and approaches across study levels in a program, more authentic and impactful assessment approaches, etc.

I also measure success in terms of my influence on the pedagogical capacity of the academic community I work with, e.g. providing advice or resources that build the educational knowledge and skills of academics in my faculty. This includes identifying and disseminating authentic peer learning examples (e.g. assessment designs), so academic colleagues can learn from one another's approaches.

Intermediate 5-7 years

- 1) Student success
- 2) Staff enablement
- 3) Efficient continuous improvement and quality assurance processes for delivering high quality education
- 4) Undertaking education research and evaluation for publishing.

My goal is to iteratively improve our offerings one step at a time, upskill and mentor our teachers to help them be better educators and change organisational and local processes to incorporate sound pedagogical practices.

I do a lot of observational work and reflection on what I see in the activities and materials of a subject, together with quantitative data analysing student performance around particular concepts, having teachers I work with share back their key findings which I compare against my expectations, as well as the usual mix of surveys and focus groups.

Very broadly – to support my school in delivering the best educational opportunities for our students and enable them to go forth and be well equipped for their future lives. More specifically though, the two primary goals would be

- 1) to assist in finding critical areas for improvement and determining the best way to address these (i.e. 1:1 work with academics, or creating professional development opportunities) and
- 2) fostering a supporting culture that looks to promote best practice and innovative approaches.

I find measuring success is generally difficult as there are many factors that will influence outcomes. But I generally look at (in no particular order) SETU feedback from students (general but also comments about specific aspects of a unit I've worked on), staff feedback (formal/informal), staff attendance at events, various observable trends (e.g. % various assessment types). Some aspects of success are harder to measure: for example, when supporting new academics, one measure of success is when they don't need to ask me anymore.

Senior 7+ years

My role has evolved over nine years from working intensively with individual academics who wanted to try something new in their education practice – with a focus on LMS design, and assessment – which were really tangible ways into unit design more broadly. We had centrally set targets for 'enhancement' at the time, so I measured the number of units where my team had an

impact, no matter how small. Over time, though, working with successive DDEs and changing education priorities, opportunities arose for the work of my team to become more strategic. I looked at how we could effect education transformation at the course level. We did this by providing curriculum maps and reviews to course leaders, who were encouraged to lead a conversation with their teaching teams on the narrative of their programs, how skills and knowledge development should/could be scaffolded through a program via learning activities and programmatic assessment. This work is now aligned to the formal course review process, so it has become embedded in faculty practices, and leads to course level renewal. So I started small, and looked for opportunities for our work to become more integrated into existing processes. We have nurtured relationships and trust with our academic colleagues over time so that we are seen to add value to course and unit renewal. Not that we're all the way there yet – progress has been slow and we continue to seek ways to tell the stories of our impact so our academic colleagues welcome us into the conversation.

My goals are to manage the day-to-day delivery of education, support the staff who do this work and engage in projects that forward the education goals of my faculty and the wider university. I measure success by my ability to manage this workload whilst still making positive impactful contributions to the strategic education goals of the institution.

Inspiring positive changes in teaching practices to create better learning experiences and outcomes for students.

Evidence of success is mostly anecdotal, but can be found in:

- 1) academic colleague's unsolicited and solicited comments
- 2) students' comments and ratings of purpose-built surveys (e.g. regarding learning materials, multimedia, interactive activities I built or supported in building)
- 3) academics' implementation of teaching practices and awards/ recognition of those practices
- 4) professional development requested by departments in the faculty, and
- 5) collaborative project grants/ publication output.

I aim to empower people, students and educators, with the competence and confidence and love for learning and scientific research methods. I aim to enable close, progressive, open and dynamic communities which foster care for people globally and for the environment, and I strive to remove or reduce barriers to educational engagement. I measure my success through successful class, unit and course delivery in a range of metrics, including student satisfaction, student performance, and student retention. I also measure success through community health metrics such as community closeness, diversity, and my feelings around staff happiness. For example, if staff are all present and engaged and coming to me with joy and excitement and passion, I feel I have succeeded. If there is a positive learning culture in the student body, I consider myself successful. I also value positive ad hoc commentary from my peers and colleagues, and well as performance reviews.

What are some of the 'blockers' to success?

Novice 1-5 years

It can be difficult to schedule time to evaluate measurable success in a meaningful way. I think that by the nature of the work we do at university, we are always pushing to move forward to the next semester, or the next project, and don't often have the opportunity to pause and reflect.

I think one of the biggest challenges is the amount of "invisible work" that goes into our role. It's work that is often hard to quantify, can be very time-consuming, and the lines can be blurred in regard to whose responsibility the work is. Some of this comes down to pushing back on certain tasks, which I will admit I'm not very good at doing, but I think some of it also comes down to a lack of workforce planning, i.e. not enough people to do the work, and team structures not fit to accommodate the work properly.

Another big challenge for me, personally, is a lack of confidence in certain scenarios. Because of the many people around who hold PhDs and the like, I often have a little bit of imposter syndrome. I think this also comes down to the vast number of things that we need to advise on: I am very confident in some areas and not so confident in others. I think there's a tendency to feel like we need to be experts on everything, which is an impossible thing to be!

In my role, there are some factors that can limit my impact at times.

It is generally easiest to make successful contributions at the unit level. Unit level work can be limited by the time/resourcing available to my academic colleagues and myself, so is generally targeted / staged. Given these limitations, success can sometimes be modest or gradual. When possible I work to create impact at higher levels (e.g. program level, Area of Study/School/Faculty level), where I would say that the key barrier again can be academic colleagues' scarcity of time or attention. Building ongoing relationships/trust over time can address this challenge, particularly by demonstrating sensitivity to the specific contexts of different academic collaborators/ disciplines.

Another challenge relates to the place of my role / team within its organisational context, e.g. the relative standing of professional and academic staff, occasional overlaps/ confusion/ communication gaps between my team and other teams within and outside of the faculty. These are fairly standard organisational issues and are not generally a major problem. In terms of barriers to success, I would say that the necessity to ensure buy-in/alignment from multiple organisational stakeholders can sometimes undermine my team's ability to show independent initiative and ambition — but conversely, this also means we are generally well-attuned to the practical needs of our clients/leadership, and don't over-invest in or duplicate project work.

Intermediate 5-7 years

- 1) Lack of stability/constant changes in business processes
- 2) T&R staff workload and time limitations

- 3) Support/encouragement for professional staff to pursue Ed focussed research as a part of their workload
- 4) No means to share ideas for strategic initiatives

- not having the budget or buy-in from leadership to get important work done
- overly bureaucratic processes to make major changes end up tripling the time to see any real changes
- teaching staff I work with not having the time to invest in upskilling or doing things differently
- the psychological welfare of staff

Primarily due to confounding factors – if you help design a really great assessment and rubric it can be objectively great but implemented poorly, for example. Likewise, if you contribute to a unit requiring an IUP, if it ends up a “purple” unit, the success must be attributed to many moving parts that have been effectively implemented (not just my role), so it’s hard to determine how effective my contributions were.

Additionally, academic buy-in is required for everything and becomes a condition for success. If there is not academic buy-in, it doesn’t get off the ground. I feel that academic workload and attitudes contribute to this – no doubt they have heavy workloads, especially at peak times, but I think the distance between my (professional) role and their (academic) role sometimes means they are unwilling to take on my suggestions. My perception at times is that given I am no longer at the coalface I am certainly viewed by some academics as “admin”, here to create more work for them for no good reason.

Senior 7+ years

The key frustration for me early on was that despite University and Faculty mandates for education transformation, and all the work I’d done to provide a scalable pedagogic model – which was supported by a complex mix of learning theory, blended learning methodology and instructional design principles, ‘just-in-time’ support resources, workshops – uptake across the faculty was at best uneven, with pockets of resistance to any innovation whatsoever. The work was exhausting and at times demoralising. It took me some years of trial and error, and reflection, to realise that my initial change management strategy – building relationships, working with early adopters, and showcasing exemplars of good practice – needed to be recast as a learning design, with our educators as active learning participants in their own learning. Bringing educators together in dialogic and disciplinary learning communities helps to reinforce their identity as educators and experts in their fields; acknowledge the passion, fear and pride in teaching; create a safe space for creative risk-taking; and scaffold their own development.

Probably just the amount of work that we need to do due to all the change that is occurring around us, everything is urgent, everything needs to be completely redone, nothing lasts for even 12 months.

Organisational culture and a lack of reward/ promotion structure that recognise and celebrate teaching as much as does research. We often get to work with teaching-focussed academics, or T&R academics who are passionate about teaching, or academics who are “required” to work with us. However, there is a great portion who either don’t prioritise teaching or simply don’t have the time to dedicate to teaching.

Sometimes, I do not quite have the knowledge base to help educators with problems they encounter. For example, I could probably use some upskilling in universal design for learning principles, and some more digital learning environment- themed issues, such as managing H5Ps or having seamless platform interfacing. These are issues that stress educators out, and that I am sometimes having to really reach to support them. I also find that some administrative and organisation structures and infrastructure can be very limiting, particularly communications. I could use some more active inclusion in terms of being in the third space. I often fall off email lists, and people are sometimes unclear about what I am expecting from them or what they can expect from me.

What PD have you found the most valuable?

Novice 1-5 years

In terms of informal PD, I have found participating in communities of practice to be the most valuable because of the knowledge and perspectives shared.

In terms of formal PD, I have recently undertaken a postgraduate degree in digital teaching and learning, and that was invaluable for the opportunity to explore technologies and theories that I wouldn’t otherwise have been able to dedicate the time to.

The most valuable PD for me has been formal qualifications which I have had to fund myself. I’ve been wanting to do my Masters of Education since I’ve joined in this role but have found the cost to be a major barrier. I have recently commenced a Grad Cert in Education through a CSP, and in the short time that I have done it have found it to be hugely beneficial to my role as an ed designer.

Conferences are also great, which I’ve been lucky enough to have funded by the faculty. Writing papers and presenting have been so valuable, not just in developing my knowledge in SoTL but also in developing my writing and presentation skills and building my professional network.

I tend to value the sharing of practice examples and approaches from higher education T&L colleagues, via conferences, seminars, peer learning / discussion, etc. Because my role requires me to participate in curriculum design problem-solving and innovation with academics, learning about authentic approaches that others have applied can be particularly useful.

More general, non-specific PD can be useful for better understanding general principles or key concepts, but I tend to find such PD less immediately useful (e.g. general coverage of T&L concepts, introductory ed tech training, etc.) It’s often not that difficult to find online resources

that cover the basics — and the most impactful PD is more specific to my role’s current context / problems.

Intermediate 5-7 years

It’s mostly been 70/20/10 approach in terms of PD, with the majority of it coming from experience on job. Other than that I have found attending TELevisors network and other educational forums quite helpful in finding a community of belonging and source of motivation to undertake self-guided initiatives to collaborate.

I found KaosPilot to be a really helpful training which distilled together a considerably number of pedagogies and learning theories into a cohesive whole and adopts a very clear framework around the design of not just learning but any experience-based event.

I did the QM rubric course a few years ago, which at the time I found valuable in terms of having a framework to audit courses for quality: <https://www.qualitymatters.org/qa-resources/rubric-standards/higher-ed-rubric>

I have an interest in education research so I found it useful to do a course on Education Research through my faculty, which helped me to interpret literature more effectively and boost my critical thinking skills.

Attending various disciplinary education conferences also helps to stay on top of who is doing what – especially in terms of innovation. Similarly, I have appreciated the post-COVID explosion of various webinar series as they are more accessible than in-person events.

Senior 7+ years

In an effort to make my work more visible, I have concentrated my PD efforts on conference presentations and publications, and journal articles, in collaboration with ed design and academic colleagues – although the time available for this work does get pushed out by more pressing BAU deadlines. The one thing I have found most valuable for myself professionally is to apply for HEA fellowship. The process of writing a narrative of professional practice required me to reflect on my practice and my influence for the first time, and served to align my work with educational theory and research. This has filtered back into my work where I am feeling less like an imposter and more like an expert in my field.

Attending conferences, it’s this window of time where you don’t have to be answering questions and emails constantly, and you just get to think and reflect on your work and what impactful initiatives you can engage with (even if they are not related to the conference).

I find courses on LinkedIn Learning, Coursera and other online learning platforms helpful. They are great tasters and can offer a wide range of topics from which you can choose. I am currently working towards the Google User Experience Design Certificate.

I really enjoy going to L+T conferences, particularly small or discipline-specific ones. I get key skills/workshops, bonus incidental content (like that other talk in the session that isn't the one I came along for but was completely great and relevant), and the networking is invaluable.

Do you have some further advice to share with colleagues?

Novice 1-5 years

Collaborate with each other as much as possible. We all have such varied backgrounds and wisdom, and it's so much fun to share and learn from each other.

Be flexible, be open to learning new things, collaborate with others as much as you can, build good quality relationships, continue to study (if you can), identify a few areas of interest/ specialisation, attend conferences & engage with professional networks.

It's hard to think of catch-all career advice, because ED roles cover a range of niches, with people from different professional backgrounds. The most valuable skill that cuts across all contexts may be the ability to narrate stories of significant impact related to ED work. It can be challenging to delineate the impact of one's individual ED contributions (or an ED team's contributions) from the work of academic colleagues, other organisational teams, etc. So my advice might focus on reflectively documenting and narrating impactful work, from goal-setting to review of impact. The goals of ED work are often set by academics based on the challenges they face in their teaching context — but EDs (consciously or not) can play a valuable role in helping academics to define the educational problems, and the goals and methods to address them (e.g. by drawing upon concepts from SOTL and relevant practice examples).

Intermediate 5-7 years

Be proactive. Join the TELedvisors Network and other CoPs and get active on LinkedIn. Find friendtots (experienced people working in the same area as you who can be your well-wishers, director of honesty and mentor). If you think of an idea or come across an opportunity, talk to your manager and try to provide a rationale for how it aligns with the Faculty/School/Division's vision.

Take all the opportunities you have to show off your work and how great you are as this becomes necessary evidence to others that you know what you're talking about.

If your role allows, carve out projects that are genuinely of interest to you to keep the motivation going.

Senior 7+ years

Find a mentor, probably from outside your regular team/faculty. Find a learning community where you can test out ideas. Begin any project with an exploration of data and scholarly literature. Reflect on your practice and investigate where you can influence others' practice. Manage up where necessary to ensure you have a seat at the table!

Always try to design things that make people's life easier: no-one likes more complexity or additional work. This will make you shine!

1. Collaboration is key.
2. Learn new skills. An ed designer needs to solve problems, sometimes from multiple angles. Having a diverse skillset will be very useful.

Absolutely! Be communicative and proactive. This role does not just exist or just “happen”. It is crafted and curated and guided constantly, and has to be actively integrated into the T+L community, either through formal processes and procedures, but also in terms of more organic staff interactions and social structures. The deference of leadership to your authority in ed design is critical for educators to find you relevant and valuable. If all of these things aren't working ideally, speak up! Be clear about what you expect from the role, and where you can take it. It is an active role, always. Make it go, make it grow.

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